

CORMAC MCCARTHY'S ALL THE PRETTY HORSES IS A BILDUNGSROMAN NOVEL

L. Mahalakshmi* & Dr. M. Leelavathi**

* Assistant Professor & Head, Department of English, Sasurie College of Arts & Science, Vijayamangalam, Tirupur, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor & Head, PG & Research Department of English, LRG Government Arts College for Women, Tirupur, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: L. Mahalakshmi & Dr. M. Leelavathi, "Cormac McCarthy's *All the Pretty Horses* is a Bildungsroman Novel", *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research*, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 219-221, 2017

Abstract:

Bildungsroman is a novel which deals about the development of a central character of any novel or drama. The main character experiences some moral growth. Bildungsroman is a German word which was introduced by Karl Morgenstern and was popularized by Wilhelm Dilthey in the 20th century especially in storytelling. This type of novel deals about the hero's growth in the natural world and how he will be suffering to come up in his life throughout the play or novel. In this novel *All the Pretty Horses* John Grady's character tells the sufferings and feelings as young boy how he comes out of it. At the young age he comes out of the desire of owning his grandfather's ranch, and the parental care and the expectation which he cannot experienced from his parents. After the emotional and material loss the protagonist plans to come out of his house and his own country. The psychological development of the protagonist reveals after taking his own desire here and there throughout the novel John Grady experiences the struggling physically and mentally and tackles everything with his own courage and passion.

Key Words: Bildungsroman, Sufferings, Expectation, Emotional, Protagonist, Physically, Tackles & Passion

Introduction:

Bildungsroman novel is a development of an individual growth and development of character. Throughout the novel or story, the main character survives with hurdles that start from early ages, education, parental care, employment survival, degradation. When the novel develops its full summary the hero's physical and mental development nurtured into some meaningful position.. The theme of the story Bildungsroman is applied for only the maturity of the main character or protagonist of the story. In *All the Pretty Horses* the hero John Grady lacks in any of the features and wants to survive for his betterment. Grady's momentous incidents will occur it may be best or worst but he is supposed to be in a position to tackle everything McCarthy deals about the hero's search for identity, love and true friendship. John Grady a teenage boy feels helpless after his grandfather's death and receives nothing from his parents. He does not have any emotional bondage at home which means love and care. He decides to leaves out of the home by accompanying his young age friend Rawlins. Rawlins also leaves the home because of Grady he is affectionate and true friend of Grady.

The youthful protagonist experience the intense pain, and losses everything, his grandfather and the mother's selling of the ranch as an ancestral property is a major problem. He cannot understand about his father's resources and his life because Grady was not there to witness it, and his father cannot adequately convey his experience as a soldier and what he earned for his son. John Grady become helpless even he lives with both the father and mother. The lack of parental care and love is the first struggle which was experienced and then the funerals of his grandfather and father. Though the protagonist has the right to own the ranch as a heir of his grandfather's ranch he is ignored by his own mother after his grandfather's death.

The first man to die in the Cole's house is his grandfather, according to John Grady, on the tradition embodied in the ranch; the boy laments for his ancestor's death and has the desire to remain in the ranch like his grandfather. But his mother's ignorance all his dreams and desires about the ranch is broken into pieces. He cannot be helped by his father to protect the ranch, as a husband he is not in the position to argue his wife."But if it hadn't of been for her I wouldn't of made it" (26). Grady came to understand the father's real position of helplessness. John Grady's mother status as owner and heir of the ranch decides to sell the ranch. Grady is not at all willing to speak with his mother instead he listen her acting in a play, here Grady understands his mother is not in a position to listen to his son and give meaningful life. However he loses the inherited property and recognizes the incompatibility of his perspective with others around him.

Grady wants to alienate from his present society, had conversation with his father, and they both were discusses about the horse and it is a symbol of natural truth and beauty, and the father presents a saddle to Grady, signifies the fathers approval and for setting out on his own. He starts his revolution alone with his true friend Lacy Rawlins moves to Mexico by taking their horse. Here the protagonist's moral development grows by finding job and searching for a lovable life. The maturation of the protagonist is the most prominent and through the journey from one place to another place gives a great change to Grady. After a great loss of his, grandfather and the failure of getting his grandfather's ranch he starts the journey. The journey of the protagonist is not easy in this novel, Grady and his friend used to meet strangers, thieves and a new companion

Jimmy Blevins a liar joins along with these two friends and says that the horse he came by is his own horse and at last John and Rawlins came to know that horse was stolen one. Within few days of travel they reach to Mexico they meet a group of nomadic trader and purchase homemade liquor. After finding out Blevins horse the three were followed by armed men and Blevins is separated from the friends Grady and Rawlins. John is the only person who is able to negotiate with the stranger and others and John Grady as a cow boy portrayed as a skilled person possessed with the abilities of handling the varieties of horses. In bildungsroman theme the central character is developed through some kind of education and moral development but in All the Pretty Horses Grady develops with different kind of skill like any hero possesses.

John Grady's new life starts after meeting a group of vaqueros driving a herd of cattle and inquired about their work. They took them to the ranch where they live; the ranch called La Purisma, comprises 11,000 hectares and is owned by Don Hector Rocha Y Villarreal a rich man conducts an interview with John Grady;

What is your opinion of the mares, he said

There are some good mares in the bunch.

Yes. Do you know a horse called Three Bars?

That's a thoroughbred horse.

You know the horse.....

Tell me about the horses up on the mesa (117).

John Grady and Don Hector have long conversation about horse varieties and their behaviors. John shows his adventures through his strong will power of tackling with the powerful horses. His enthusiasm and knowledge about the new kind of horses which other vaqueros do not know. In this way Don Hector is much impressed and gives a job in his ranch. John Grady's career development and his big dream of working with horses are achieved here. After lot of struggling and pain he is able to survive with the horses in Don Hector's ranch with his fellow companion Jack Rawlins. This achievement is also a proof of the hero's development. He enjoys working in the ranch and with horses. His succession and enjoyment in the ranch is confined only few days. In order to lead a successful career Grady get diverted his mind after seeing Alejandra the daughter of a ranch owner. Protagonist's next struggle starts in this novel by the implication of love towards Alejandra. The love between the pair will continue till Alejandra's aunt came to know about their affair.

The attraction between John Grady and Alejandra grows. They begin to meet in secretly and they love each other. The enjoyment between the lovers continues for a short span of time. Even though Alejandra's aunt Alfonsa advices Grady not to see Alejandra anymore, without minding Grady makes love with her, Alfonsa explains what is happened in her life and how her life is spoiled because of the love affair. The young lover never minding they continue their love making, at last Alejandra's father decides to send his daughter to Europe for higher studies and Grady is captured by the police. The armed men capture John Grady and Rawlins the last relationship of Grady is ended apathetically but he grows up in all capacities of true hero good friend of Rawlins, a lover to Alejandra and a mentor to Blevins and most importantly he has lost his innocence without becoming disillusioned. When he leaves San Angelo again at the end of the novel, he is become a hardened hero and also a wise one his spirit is no longer defined by its emptiness but by its completeness.

John Grady's courage and valor shows throughout the novel, when he comes out of his native country, when meeting with strangers choosing a career in a ranch, love affair with ranch owner's daughter, fighting with prisoners and at last succeeded to come out of the ranch and meets Alejandra. He again joined in some kind of relationship and succeeds to meet Alejandra again. He involves the commitment what he wants and being a moralist he never thinks about god and rarely talks about god, he preferred to follow his own moral values and principles. In the prison he feels sad about miserable situation happening his friend Rawlins and also Jimmy Blevins. Rawlins also blame his true friend and his deeds for capturing by the Mexican police. His dream of running horses the novel praises the "resonance" of the world itself, which cannot be spoken but only praised. His true love and friendship is praised by the critics but at last he is separated from both, the love and care which he gets from the beginning till the end is questionable from his parents and lover notwithstanding Grady's courage his loss of feelings continuous till the end, he leaves everything, his long lasting friend becomes a stranger and his lover Alejandra manipulated by her aunt Alfonse leaves John Grady. John Grady leaves everything and moves west part of the Texas. At the end of the novel shows the protagonist's defeat it inevitable but the hero's courage and valor never fades. Even though John Grady as a cowboy his personal insistence and personal destiny is denied and he struggles against the social barriers and overwhelming odds.

Gail Moore Morrison in his article John Grady Cole's Expulsion from Paradise in Perspectives on Cormac McCarthy states that "this novel fundamentally a Bildungsroman is a coming of age story in the great tradition of Hawthorne, Twain, Melville and James, that archetypal American genre in which a youthful protagonist turns his back on civilization and heads out into the forest, down river, across the sea or, as in John Grady's through desert and mountain on horseback into the wilderness where innocence experiences the evil of the universe and risks defeat by it.

Conclusion:

Bildungsroman novel focuses about the theme of hero`s education and development in any novel, in *All the Pretty Horses* sporadically deals about the boy who has less graduation, but has the traits of a hero and experiences many trials which is fateful and unexpected one throughout his life. The hero`s physical and moral growth develops within the circle of love and failure.

References:

1. McCarthy, Cormac. *All the Pretty Horses*; 2002, Macmillan Publishers Limited.
2. Fry, Steven, *The Cambridge Companion to Cormac McCarthy*.
3. Arnold, Edwin T and Luce, Dianne C. *Perspectives on Cormac McCarthy*. British Library Cataloging-in- Publications.
4. <http://study.com/academy/lesson/bildungsroman-definition-characteristics-examples.html>